

NAVIGATING PHYSICAL EDUCATION LEARNING EXPERIENCES: STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVE AND ADAPTATION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 7

Pages: 710-716

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2698

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14354857

Manuscript Accepted: 11-12-2024

Navigating Physical Education Learning Experiences: Students' Perspective and Adaptation

Julie Christine P. Ladan*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study determined the learning experiences, perspective, and adaptation in Physical Education during the transition from pandemic to face-to-face learning modality. The researcher utilized a phenomenological approach. The respondents of the research were 10 students from public schools named Labangal National High School, Irineo High School and General Santos City SPED Integrated School. The data were gathered through a series of personal interviews to the students to gather the qualitative data, describing their experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms. A researcher-made interview guide was used in gathering the qualitative data. The interview guide underwent validation by experts in qualitative research, specifically those with expertise in phenomenological approaches. Subsequent to the validation, a pilot test was conducted to confirm the instrument's accuracy, establish rapport with participants, and refine interviewing skills. The questions in the interview guide focused on the statement of the problem. Results show that the transition from modular to face-to-face learning modality had helped students to learn and engage more in the subject, Physical Education. It revealed six major themes namely Experiential Enlightenment, Active Involvement, Interpersonal Dynamics and Perceptual Shifts, Academic Barriers, and Collective Adaptive Synergy. Face-to-face class was effective in promoting engagement and enjoyment. Despite the challenges, students showed resilience, aiding teachers in creating conducive environments, seeing the transition positively, stressing its importance for academic growth and well-being. Recommendations include continuous assessment, physical activity integration, collaborative learning encouragement, regular teacher-learner communication, more fitness activities, sustained parental support, educational plan alignment, and future research encouragement.

Keywords: *learning experiences, physical education, pandemic, face-to-face learning modality, transition*

Introduction

Physical Education is a significant component in the well-rounded education of students aiming for holistic development. Outside of the conventional classroom, Physical Education provides a distinct learning atmosphere where physical activity becomes a tool to improve mental, social, and emotional health in addition to physical fitness. However, challenges such as limited access to sports equipment, hands-on activities, budget and limited number of instructors create difficulties for both students in learning and teachers teaching the subject. According to Turner et al. (2017), their research indicated that numerous schools failed to offer sufficient time for students in physical education. Additionally, the budgets allocated for equipment in physical education programs are often minimal or entirely absent.

The wake of the pandemic has introduced myriad challenges that made an impact to student's learning experiences in Physical Education. The COVID-19 has without a doubt been one of the most transformative events of the 21st century, affecting all aspects of individuals' life, with no exceptions in the education system. Students have had to adjust to a new learning method that presents unique challenges as a result of many schools moving to remote learning. Physical Education classes, specifically, have been impacted by the pandemic, with customary in-person classes being supplanted by virtual examples. Students and educators face new challenges as a result of the shift to remote learning, such as limited equipment access, a lack of social interaction, and decreased motivation.

As the pandemic evolved and the roll-out of COVID-19 vaccinations, school systems started to progress from modular classes to hybrid classes and finally to face-to-face classes. In accordance with Galvez's (2022) report, the Department of Education has undergone a revision in its prior directive. This revision provides schools with the flexibility to select from three instructional modalities: full-time face-to-face classes, entirely remote learning, or a blended learning approach. The blended learning model entails a combination of face-to-face instruction for three days and remote learning for two days, or alternatively, four days of face-to-face classes and one day of remote learning. Furthermore, the memorandum issued by the Department of Education mandates that both public and private educational institutions transition to full face-to-face classes by the specified date of November 2, 2022.

The transition from modular, hybrid and face-to-face classes presents a critical stage in the education system because it needs to be guaranteed that the return to face-to-face classes in public schools that offered modular classes and shifted to face-to-face classes is carried out successfully and productively. Switching from modular to face-to-face lectures entails a variety of complicated and varied challenges as well as possible benefits. At the opening of public-school classes, numerous difficulties surfaced. The restrictions of face-to-face classes have essentially impacted the performance of the teachers and students according to Cabello (2022). Students had a hard time reading, writing and comprehending instructions because they were put further behind their skills. Due to the longest schools closure for over 70 weeks as of the center of February brought about by the Coronavirus pandemic, De Vera (2022) said that under 15% of students in the Philippines, or around 3 out of 20, can only read basic texts in reading materials.

This study aims to fill this gap and investigate how students learned physical education in public schools when transitioning from modular to face-to-face classes. This had looked into the particular difficulties that students had learned and to shed light on the unique challenges and opportunities that arise in the context of modular and face-to-face physical education. Furthermore, this study examined the perspectives and insights of students themselves revealing a comprehensive understanding of the specific factors that impeded their progress, and examining potential solutions to these problems. By exploring students' experiences, perceptions, and learning outcomes during the shift, this research endeavored to identify effective strategies for educators and institutions to improve the overall learning experience for Physical Education students. Ultimately, the findings might contribute to enhancing the pedagogical approaches in Physical Education settings and enable institutions to create more adaptive and engaging learning environments. It is worth noting that there exists a limited amount of literature that examines the shift from modular to face-to-face classes, emphasizing the importance of this investigation in bridging this particular void in the current academic milieu.

Research Questions

This study described the learning experiences of Junior High School students in Physical Education during the transition from modular distance learning to face-to-face modality. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What are the learning experiences of the students in Physical Education?
2. How do students' perspectives in physical education change as a result of transition?
3. How do students adapt during the transition?

Literature Review

Learning Experiences

The learning experience of students in Physical Education extends beyond conventional classroom aims to foster holistic education through different physical activities. In Physical Education, students learn not just the component but also hopes to improve the academic performance of the students. Kohl et al. (2013) conducted a study indicating that there is an evidence supporting the idea that enhancing physical activity and fitness levels can lead to improvements in academic performance. The study also suggests that allocating time within the school day for activities such as recess, physical education classes, and incorporating physical activity in the classroom may contribute to enhanced academic performance.

The learning experience in Physical Education was a challenge during the pandemic due to reduced interpersonal contact. Peñas (2022) stated that students feel to have issues in understanding and following instructions, and the learning activities are complex and seem to be too tough for them since they will be working alone. These can link to their lack of readiness in Modular Learning Modality, as it engages them unassisted with lesser school teachers' interventions.

However, with the dedicated efforts of healthcare professionals, there was a gradual transition from online modality to face-to-face learning modality. According to Villar et al. (2022) it is evident that the previous academic year is totally different from what the schools used to have, and not what anyone intends to experience. Yet, through the collaborative efforts of the educational and community sectors, a significant progress was experienced by some of the learners when reopening of classes was made possible and face-to-face classes are allowed, though it is still limited because of COVID 19.

Moreover, as the transition from modular to face-to-face learning occurs, students can provide a safe space, fostering healthy connections with other students. This shift also enables them to appreciate the advantages bestowed upon them through Physical Education, cultivating a sense of gratitude. Kumar (2017) emphasizes the significance of physical education and sports as an integral component of education. This discipline directly contributes to the development of physical competence and fitness, instilling an awareness of the importance of leading an active lifestyle among the youth. A physically active and healthy youth is more likely to exhibit academic motivation, attentiveness, and promise. In essence, physical education and sports hold a distinctive position within the school's core curriculum, offering unique opportunities for youth to acquire motor skills and enhance both mental and physical fitness. The benefits derived from physical activity extend to disease prevention, safety awareness, injury avoidance, decreased morbidity, reduced premature mortality, and improved mental health.

Academic Performance

The pandemic is a big challenge and has caused a big change in the education system which affects the academic performance of students. The academic achievement of students throughout the transition from modular to face-to-face classrooms is an important factor that should be carefully examined. This shift in learning settings has the potential to affect several aspects of students' academic achievement, such as understanding, engagement, interaction with peers and instructors, and ability to adjust to new teaching approaches and classroom dynamics.

A study by Dogan et al. (2021) found that students faced challenges in understanding module classes during the pandemic due to the lack of in-person interaction with teachers and peers. They reported that students often struggle with motivation, engagement, and understanding the course material. This claim was strengthened by the study of Tan et al. (2021) because it was found that some students struggled with modular classes due to factors such as a lack of structure, difficulty with time management, and challenges

with self-directed learning. The study found that these challenges were associated with higher rates of failing grades and lower levels of comprehension.

With the transition to face-to-face classes, students are once again confronted with a significant challenge as they strive to adapt to the new mode of learning. The outcome of the research conducted by Bordeos et al. (2022) reinforces the statement mentioned above, as the teachers involved in the study expressed, students do not want to participate face-to-face since two years ago, they managed their own time; they can watch TV and do their module when it suits them, they can also play when they want without having to think too much about their schoolwork because they can just google the answers.

Reframing

The negotiated opposing perceptions of students in Physical Education plays a vital role in shaping their overall efficacy. Physical education has a unique lens through the view of students in terms of physical activity, health and their well-being. As outlined in the research conducted by Mashud and Nemeth (2022), junior high school students' perspectives on the concept of physical education falls within the "very good" category. This indicates a comprehensive understanding among students regarding the overall definition, purpose, and characteristics of activities related to the subject of physical education.

The view of Physical Education has undergone a notable transformation because of the shift of learning modality. What was once perceived positively, became dull and difficult. In their research, Duran and Sumagang (2022) conveyed that students, while delving into the challenges of transitioning to modular distance learning, expressed the difficulty of learning in the current scenario due to numerous distractions. Compounding the situation, certain educators mandated the punctual submission of modules through an educational platform. As per the participants' perspectives, modules were seen as a means to encourage self-directed learning.

The shift back to face-to-face classes has been transformative, with students now finding the subject more engaging, enjoyable, and conducive to enhanced learning experiences. According to Wahid et al. (2023) they mentioned in their study that students believe that in-person learning is significantly more effective and efficient. The claim was supported by the study of Salamuddin (2021) that states that the students concurred that face-to-face learning approach has much added to their learning than modular distance learning approach. They were propelled to learn new things where bunch conversation occurred dissimilar to in particular. Furthermore, face-to-face proficiency approach can support their confidence and creates Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) that can really help them in expanding their scholastic performance.

Beyond the varied perceptions and evolving attitudes of students toward a subject, the perspective of students regarding their teachers' teaching styles is crucial. This is because students not only gain subject-specific knowledge but also learn how to learn most effectively through the teaching methods employed by their teachers. According to Zalech (2021), a PE teacher's positive image plays a crucial role in creating a supportive educational environment and boosting motivation among students, leading to more effective promotion of positive attitudes towards physical activity. Recognizing the competencies valued by students helps identify areas for improvement during the educational process. Teachers striving for positive student perception should focus on enhancing communication and group work skills, creating a positive atmosphere that encourages greater involvement, and conducting engaging classes.

Emotional Health

The transition from modular to face-to-face learning modalities has elicited a spectrum of emotions among students, marking a significant shift in their educational experiences. It was a new yet familiar feeling for most of the students. As they explore through this change, the unconstrained responses uncover an embroidery of versatility and commitment, enhancing the learning venture in this evolving modality. Returning to face-to-face instruction can elicit a range of feelings, including worry, enthusiasm, and even melancholy (Bazley, 2021).

Recognizing the emotional terrain in this transition is vital for educators and policymakers in establishing nurturing and impactful learning environments. Despite fear of the opening of classes, students have also recognized the benefits and the excitement of going to school. According to a study by Arlinda et al. (2021), face-to-face instruction has an impact on students' motivation to learn in the classroom. Students who receive limited face-to-face instruction also exhibit increased motivation to learn.

Obstacles in Learning

The way in which students learn has been significantly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, presenting a multitude of challenges that students must overcome in order to pursue their education. The shift from modular to face-to-face classes is not an exception when it comes to the challenges students face in their learning journey. Such difficulties include social isolation, low motivation, and struggles in adapting to learning modality.

During the height of the pandemic, students have experienced a lot of challenges that hindered their learning progress that until now they are facing. One challenge that they are experiencing during the transition is the difficulty in comprehending the instructions. It was mentioned in the study of Bordeos et al. (2022) that the main challenges for students attending limited face-to-face classes were a lack of instructional time and collaboration, difficulty understanding the lessons and activities, and an adjustment period.

In addition, the study of Bordeos et al. (2022) points out that the requirement for instructional time was the biggest barrier for students

who took part in the limited face-to-face classes. Another difficulty they discovered was a lack of teamwork; because of the threat presented by the Covid-19 virus, students are not authorized to accomplish duties such as group activities and are expected to keep social distance at all times. With the shift of the modality again students were dealing with the difficulties of adjusting to the set up. It is because they had had the opportunity to witness blended learning for a few years, Students were already accustomed to the new normal. Because of this, the majority of students are attempting to adjust as life gradually returns to regular, face-to-face classes (Durana, 2022).

Coping Mechanisms

As they navigate this transformation, various challenges and adjustments come into play. To effectively manage the intricacies of this transition, students often employ coping mechanisms that enable them to adapt, thrive, and succeed in the face-to-face learning environment.

Some coping mechanisms that students have adopted to manage the challenges of learning during the COVID-19 pandemic include maintaining a routine, seeking social support, and practicing self-care. A study by Huang et al (2020) found out that students who maintained a routine and structure in their daily lives reported better psychological well-being during the pandemic. As strengthened by Lazarus and Folkman's model, it explained that successful coping mechanism depends on the emotional function associated with the problem. Lazarus categorized these eight emotional functions as follows: Confrontation; Social Care; Emotional Separation; Escape and Avoidance; Fundamental Acceptance; Positive Close Examination; Strategic Problem Solving. (Macalisang, 2021).

Despite challenges and obstacles during the new normal, students have come up with different coping mechanisms that can help them and other students in adapting to changes. Asebo et al. (2021) have stated that some students help their classmates and PE teachers by making teachers and classmates unaware that the situation is stressful, using various excuses to avoid stressful situations and students increase their efforts, plans, and practices by asking for information.

In addition, the study of Kwaah and Essilfie (2017) reveals that students use proactive coping strategies such as praying and avoiding negative stress, see what is going on, learn from experience, live with it, and find emotional support from friends and family. Baharudin (2022) also stated that there is always evidence that when parents are involved, their children perform better. Therefore, parental involvement in their children's education is crucial and could benefit everyone. As they navigate this transformation, various challenges and adjustments come into play. To effectively manage the intricacies of this transition, students often employ coping mechanisms that enable them to adapt, thrive, and succeed in the face-to-face learning environment.

Methodology

Participants

The participants of the study are students who are enrolled in schools in General Santos City specifically, Labangal National High School, Irineo National High School and GSC SPED Integrated School. The subjects are high school students who are enrolled in public school in the school year of 2023-2024. The intention of choosing the participants is to ensure that they who could give substantive information about their lived experiences in learning the subject, Physical Education, during the transition of modular distance learning to face-to-face class.

Instrument

The data were collected through the phenomenological where three research questions were asked. The researcher used an interview guide in gathering the qualitative data. The questions in the interview guide focused on the statement of the problem. The interview guide crafted by the researcher underwent validation. Selected experts who are in qualitative studies, particularly in phenomenological approach, validated the tool, making sure it gathered the necessary data to answer the statement of the problem. These experts are sourced from Master Teachers in the Department of Education (Division of General Santos City) and Notre Dame of Dadiangas University. For the post-validation, narrative feedback suggested enhancements in the English to Bisaya translation's grammar and spelling, and a reduction in question quantity. The researcher implemented these modifications to refine the research instrument. Subsequent to the validation, a pilot test was conducted to confirm the instrument's accuracy, establish rapport with participants, and refine interviewing skills.

Procedure

The researcher wrote letters, asking permission to conduct the study. The researcher invited the student to participate in the conduct of the study, gave them the assurance of confidentiality of their answers and assigned them anonymous names to hide their identity. The data gathering started with finding the participants, students, based on the criteria being set. Those who expressed their availability and willingness were invited to in depth interviews. The interviewer collected the data privately to ensure the confidentiality of the answers and the identity of the participants. The researcher got the approval of the participants on the use of a tape recorder to record the interviews. After the interviews, the researcher did the transcriptions of the recorded interviews. Then the researcher returned to the participants to process the first validation of the qualitative data. Later, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the data. The researcher went back to the participants to process the second validation of the data. Finally, the researcher made a summary of the qualitative

data, drew conclusions from them and made some recommendations about the results of the study.

Ethical Considerations

Several ethical considerations were considered and modified to ensure that the study was conducted in an appropriate manner (Bryman & Bell, 2007). The researcher observed and addressed the protocol in conducting the study. After the validation of the interview, assent form and informed consent was given to the schools where the participants are under. The school was well-informed about the study's methods and purpose. Prior to data collection, participants granted consent, with a focus on ensuring confidentiality and anonymity to address any privacy concerns. The principle of Voluntary Participation underscored participants' autonomy, emphasizing their right to withdraw without facing repercussions. The vital step of communication of results was taken, expressing gratitude for participants' valuable contributions and completing the ethical research cycle.

In addressing Transferability, the researcher supplied comprehensive, factual data on participants' experiences in learning Physical Education during the transition from modular to face-to-face learning. This not only fosters understanding but also provides opportunities for application in program development or future research. Prioritizing Dependability, the study consistently applied qualitative research protocols in data collection, maintaining reliability by asking all participants the same set of questions. Confirmability was diligently ensured by allowing participants to validate findings, promoting accurate interpretation of their words and reinforcing the study's impartiality.

Results and Discussion

This chapter comprehensively outlines the process of presenting the key findings obtained from the research, delving into the meticulous analysis and synthesis of identified themes, culminating in the synthesis of these individual themes into a cohesive and overarching general finding.

Presentation of Key Findings

The key findings on the students learning experiences of students from the different school districts of General Santos City in the Students' learning experience, perspective and adaptation in transition from modular to face-to-face classes of Physical Education revealed six major themes namely Experiential Enlightenment, Active Involvement, Interpersonal Dynamics and Perceptual Shifts, Academic Barriers, Psychological Reflex and Collective Adaptive Synergy.

Presentation of Themes into General Findings

The general finding encapsulates a comprehensive exploration of themes arising from a diverse array of Physical Education experiences, perspectives, and adaptations among Junior High School students navigating the transition from modular to face-to-face classes. Throughout the ensuing qualitative data presentations, the findings are meticulously elucidated and structured within tables, providing a detailed and insightful analysis of the research outcomes.

Table 1. *Learning Experiences of Physical Education Students*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Acquired Proficiency	Experiential Enlightenment
Positive Personal Growth	
Developed Lifestyle Modification	
Active Engagement	Active Involvement
Active Interaction	Academic Barriers
Adjustment Difficulties	
Social Hesitation	
Performance Hurdles	

Table 1 presents the thematic analysis of the learning experiences of students in Physical Education, particularly the cluster themes of the first, second and third major themes. For the first emergent theme, Experiential Enlightenment, 3 theme clusters were identified, namely: Acquired Proficiency, Positive Personal Growth and Developed Lifestyle Modifications. While on the second emergent theme, Active Involvement, with 2 theme clusters identified, namely: Active Engagement and Active Interaction. On the third emergent theme, Academic Barriers, with 3 theme clusters identified, namely: Adjustment Difficulties, Social Hesitation and Performance Hurdles.

Table 2. *Perspective of Physical Education Students*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Contrasting Perceptions	Interpersonal Dynamics and Perceptual Shifts
Positive Perceptions	
Collaborative Growth	

Table 2 reveals the third major theme that emerged during the semi structured in-depth interview with the research participants. The third theme, Interpersonal Dynamics, and Perceptual Shift identified 3 clustered themes, namely: Contrasting Perceptions, Positive Perceptions and Collaborative Growth.

Table 3. *Adaptation of Physical Education Students*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Emotional Response	Psychological Reflex
Health Concerns	
Self Adaptation	Collective Adaptive Synergy
Adaptation Through Peers	
Family Support	

Delving into the experiences of Junior High School students, Table 3 showcases the fifth and sixth major theme that emerged during the semi-structured in-depth interview with the research participants. The fifth major theme, Psychological Reflex, listed 2 theme clusters such as Emotional Response and Health Concerns. The sixth major theme, Collective Adaptive Synergy, 3 theme clusters were identified namely: Self Adaptation, Adaptation Through Peers and Family Support.

The lived experiences of Junior High School students in transition from modular to face-to-face Physical Education classes were justified based on the relevant statements revealed in the following emergent themes: Experiential Enlightenment; Active Involvement; Interpersonal Dynamics and Perceptual Shifts; Emotional Reflex; Challenges; and Collective Adaptive Synergy. The general findings of themes derived from the relevant statements shared by the Junior High School students on their lived experiences during the transition of Physical Education from modular to face-to-face classes.

The study reveals significant insights into students' experiences transitioning from modular to face-to-face learning in Physical Education. It underscores the importance of experiential learning, active involvement, and the role of interpersonal dynamics in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes. The findings suggest educational institutions should focus on fostering environments that encourage active engagement, support adaptive strategies, and address psychological and academic barriers to maximize the benefits of face-to-face learning. This approach not only improves physical education experiences but also contributes to overall student growth and wellbeing.

Conclusions

The transition from modular to face-to-face learning modality unveils a lot of aspects in understanding the learners' experiences, perception and adaptations during the shifting in the modality in Physical Education. The shift has a significant impact on students' proficiency, particularly in terms of their personal development and perception of physical education in general. Face-to-face setups are shown to be more effective than modular formats, fostering greater participation and a deeper connection with the subject. In a traditional learning environment, the participants find the subject more engaging and enjoyable.

Additionally, transition also prompts a positive shift in students' perceptions towards Physical Education, despite the challenges and mixed emotions experienced during the change. They have also taken the initiative to assist teachers in facilitating a positive teaching and learning environment. Students are able to adjust and interact with others well despite difficulties. Students generally see the shift as beneficial and positive, despite worries about the pandemic, highlighting the significance of in-person instruction for growth and wellbeing.

References

- Arlinda, R., Wuryandani, W., & Mustadi, A. (2022). The effect of limited face-to-face learning in new normal era towards learning motivation of elementary school students. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 14(3), 2963-2972.
- Åsebø, E., & Løvoll, H. (2021). Exploring coping strategies in physical education: A qualitative case study. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2021.1976743>
- Baharudin, A., Chin, Y., Nayar, A., & Shamsul, S. (2022). Parent's involvement and challenges in students learning during pandemic. *Mathematical Statistician and Engineering Applications*, 71(3), 1808-1818.
- Bazley, E. (2021). Creating a smooth transition back to face-to-face learning. Retrieved from <https://www.clickview.com.au/blog/teaching-strategies/transitioning-back-facetoface-learning/>
- Bordeos, M. (2021). Learning goes on: Students' attitudes and perceptions in the implementation of the modular distance learning during Covid-19 pandemic. *Instabright International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(1), 07-16.
- Bordeos, M. L., Lagman, K. R. M., & Cruz, I. P. S. (2022). Students in the new normal: Their experiences in the pandemic's limited face-to-face classes. *American Journal of Education and Technology*, 1(3), 42-51.
- Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2007). Business research methods. Retrieved from <https://research-methodology.net/researchmethodology/ethicalconsiderations/>
- Cabello, C. A. (2022). Higher education professors in blended learning modality of teaching: The silent tears of heroes towards. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(3), 6171-6183.

- Crawford, M. (2020). Ecological Systems theory: Exploring the development of the theoretical framework as conceived by Bronfenbrenner. *J Pub Health Issue Pract*, 4(2), 170.
- De Vera, B. (2022). Lockdown's impact: Unicef cites poor reading skills among PH kids. Retrieved from <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1576573/lockdowns-impact-unicef-cites-poor-reading-skills-among-ph-kids>
- Dogan, E., Levent, F., & Ugur, S. (2021). Students' challenges and preferences in remote learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(1), 45-64. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520968167>
- Duran, R. C. A., & Sumagang, E. Q. (2022). STEM students' experiences in modular distance learning amidst pandemic: Basis for academic interventions. *Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Education and Technology*, 1(2).
- Durana, A. (2022). Adjustments that pupils have to make as face-to-face classes return. Retrieved from <https://www.pressreader.com/philippines/panay-news/20220921/281539409816753>
- Galvez, D. (2022). DepEd: Private schools may hold hybrid, remote classes beyond November 2. Retrieved from <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1680947/depd-private-schools-may-hold-hybrid-remote-classes-beyond-nov-2>
- Huang, Y., Zhao, N., & General, W. (2020). Mental health burden for the public affected by the COVID-19 outbreak in China: Who will be the risk group? *Psychology, Health & Medicine*, 26(1), 23-34. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13548506.2020.1748481>
- Kohl III, H. W., & Cook, H. D. (Eds.). (2013). *Educating the student body: Taking physical activity and physical education to school*.
- Kumar, R. (2017). Impact of physical education and sports in promoting social values among youth. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 4(2), 88. <https://doi.org/18.01.069/20170402>
- Mashud, M., & Nemeth, Z. (2022). Physical education: Study of different perceptions of students on the concept of physical education in first middle school and vocational middle school. *Jurnal Pendidikan: Teori, Penelitian, dan Pengembangan*, 7(8), 299-308.
- Peñas, J. D. (2022). Challenges in modular learning: Teaching physical education in the midst of COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 95(1), 12-12.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). Self-determination theory. Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness.
- Salamuddin, A. A. (2021). Comparative analysis of students' perceptions in modular distance learning approach versus face-to-face learning approach of Mindanao State University–Sulu. *Open Access Indonesia Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(4), 395-407.
- Turner, L., Johnson, T. G., Calvert, H. G., & Chaloupka, F. J. (2017). Stretched too thin? The relationship between insufficient resource allocation and physical education instructional time and assessment practices. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 68, 210-219.
- Villar, M. C. G., Filipinas, J. P., Villanueva, J. B., & Cabello, C. A. (2022). The transition, transformation, and adaptation from modular-printed instruction to limited face-to-face classes: A phenomenology. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 4(9), 932-940.
- Wahid, M., Firdaus, F., Amaliah, N., Ariandi, A., Firman, F., Irfan, M., & Nurdin, M. (2023). Students' perspectives on switching from online to face-to-face learning environments after the COVID-19 pandemic. *Jurnal Pijar Mipa*, 18(2), 219-223.
- Zalech, M. (2021). Student perception of PE teachers and its effect on their participation in PE classes and sports: A new perspective on teacher competencies. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 21, 1106-1111.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Julie Christine P. Ladan

Notre Dame of Dadiangas University – Philippines